

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning is everywhere!

amazon.com.

facebook.

Google

Advertisement & social media

Robotics

Autonomous navigation

Image and speech understanding

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning is everywhere!

The New York Times

Google Researchers Are Learning How Machines Learn

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning

MIT
Technology
Review

THE
NEW YORKER

APRIL 3, 2017 ISSUE

A.I. VERSUS M.D.

What happens when diagnosis is automated?

By Siddhartha Mukherjee

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ECONOMY | CAPITAL ACCOUNT
How Robots May Make Radiologists' Jobs Easier, Not Redundant
Artificial intelligence programs that diagnose disease by analyzing images still require human judgment
By Greg Ip
Updated Nov 22, 2017 12:56 p.m. ET

Earlier this month a team of computer scientists at Stanford

January 18, 2018

AI Is Continuing Its Assault on Radiologists
A new model can detect abnormalities in x-rays better than radiologists—in some parts of the body, anyway.

www.news.cn
新华网
news
www.xinhuanet.com

XINHUANET

Monday, July

China Focus: AI beats human doctors in neuroimaging recognition contest

Web of Science: “Deep Learning”

Showing 27,171 records for TOPIC: (deep learning)

Date: 28 July 2018

The apocalyptic hype

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MUWWZ91-G6w>

Bits of history

Bits of history

- Perceptron
- Neocognitron
- CCN in the 90's
- Resurgence

NEW NAVY DEVICE LEARNS BY DOING

Psychologist Shows Embryo
of Computer Designed to
Read and Grow Wiser

WASHINGTON, July 7 (UPI)—The Navy revealed the embryo of an electronic computer today that it expects will be able to walk, talk, see, write, reproduce itself and be conscious of its existence.

The embryo—the Weather Bureau's \$2,000,000 "704" computer—learned to differentiate between right and left after fifty attempts in the Navy's demonstration for newsmen.

The service said it would use this principle to build the first of its Perceptron thinking machines that will be able to read and write. It is expected to be finished in about a year at a cost of \$100,000.

Dr. Frank Rosenblatt, designer of the Perceptron, conducted the demonstration. He said the machine would be the first device to think as the human brain. As do human be-

ings, Perceptron will make mistakes at first, but will grow wiser as it gains experience, he said.

Dr. Rosenblatt, a research psychologist at the Cornell Aeronautical Laboratory, Buffalo, said Perceptrons might be fired to the planets as mechanical space explorers.

Without Human Controls

The Navy said the perceptron would be the first non-living mechanism "capable of receiving, recognizing and identifying its surroundings without any human training or control."

The "brain" is designed to remember images and information it has perceived itself. Ordinary computers remember only what is fed into them on punch cards or magnetic tape.

Later Perceptrons will be able to recognize people and call out their names and instantly translate speech in one language to speech or writing in another language, it was predicted.

Mr. Rosenblatt said in principle it would be possible to build brains that could reproduce themselves on an assembly line and which would be conscious of their existence.

1958 New York
Times...

In today's demonstration, the "704" was fed two cards, one with squares marked on the left side and the other with squares on the right side.

Learns by Doing

In the first fifty trials, the machine made no distinction between them. It then started registering a "Q" for the left squares and "O" for the right squares.

Dr. Rosenblatt said he could explain why the machine learned only in highly technical terms. But he said the computer had undergone a "self-induced change in the wiring diagram."

The first Perceptron will have about 1,000 electronic "association cells" receiving electrical impulses from an eye-like scanning device with 400 photo-cells. The human brain has 10,000,000,000 responsive cells, including 100,000,000 connections with the eyes.

- The Perceptron

Rosenblatt, Frank (1958), The Perceptron: A Probabilistic Model for Information Storage and Organization in the Brain, Cornell Aeronautical Laboratory, Psychological Review, v65, No. 6, pp. 386–408.

Multilayer Perceptron (80's)

- Can learn nonlinear functions provided each perceptron has a differentiable nonlinearity

Training of multi-layer networks

- Find network weights to minimize the *training error* between true and estimated labels of training examples, e.g.:

$$E(\mathbf{w}) = \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - f_{\mathbf{w}}(\mathbf{x}_i))^2$$

- Update weights by gradient descent:

$$\mathbf{w} \leftarrow \mathbf{w} - \alpha \frac{\partial E}{\partial \mathbf{w}}$$

<http://playground.tensorflow.org/>

Stochastic gradient descent

- Local optimization
 - Dropping connections to escape local minima
- Vanishing gradient in many-layer networks
- Noisy:
 - moment, batch normalization, etc.
- Error landscape depends on the data sample

1980 Neocognitron

Neocognitron: A Self-organizing Neural Network Model for a Mechanism of Pattern Recognition **Unaffected by Shift in Position.**

Fukushima. 1980

25 years of feature designing...

Canny Edge Detection
Canny, 1986

Harris Corner Detection
Harris and Stephens, 1988

Harr Wavelets,
Viola and Jones, CVPR 2001

SIFT,
Lowe, 2004

HOG,
Dalal and Triggs, 2005

LeNet 5

Y. LeCun, L. Bottou, Y. Bengio, and P. Haffner, [Gradient-based learning applied to document recognition](#), Proc. IEEE 86(11): 2278–2324, 1998.

Brief History of Neural Networks

Beginnings

Thresholded Logic Unit

1943

Perceptron

1957

Adaline

1960

1st Neural Winter

XOR Problem

1969

Multilayer Backprop

1982

CNNs

1986

LSTMs

1989

1997

2nd Neural Winter

SVMs

1995

GPU Era

Deep Nets

2006

Alex Net

2012

1940

1950

1960

1970

1980

1990

2000

2010

S. McCulloch - W. Pitts

R. Rosenblatt

B. Widrow - M. Hoff

M. Minsky - S. Papert

P. Werbos

D. Rumelhart - G. Hinton - R. Williams

Y. Lecun - J. Schmidhuber

C. Cortes - V. Vapnik

R. Salakhutdinov - J. Hinton - A. Krizhevsky - I. Sutskever

Year	Breakthroughs in AI	Datasets (First Available)	Algorithms (First Proposed)
1994	Human-level spontaneous speech recognition	Spoken Wall Street Journal articles and other texts (1991)	Hidden Markov Model (1984)
1997	IBM Deep Blue defeated Garry Kasparov	700,000 Grandmaster chess games, aka "The Extended Book" (1991)	Negascout planning algorithm (1983)
2005	Google's Arabic- and Chinese-to-English translation	1.8 trillion tokens from Google Web and News pages (collected in 2005)	Statistical machine translation algorithm (1988)
2011	IBM Watson became the world Jeopardy! champion	8.6 million documents from Wikipedia, Wiktionary, Wikiquote, and Project Gutenberg (updated in 2010)	Mixture-of-Experts algorithm (1991)
2014	Google's GoogLeNet object classification at near-human performance	ImageNet corpus of 1.5 million labeled images and 1,000 object categories (2010)	Convolution neural network algorithm (1989)
2015	Google's Deepmind achieved human parity in playing 29 Atari games by learning general control from video	Arcade Learning Environment dataset of over 50 Atari games (2013)	<u>Q-learning algorithm (1992)</u>
Average No. of Years to Breakthrough:		3 years	18 years

TWEAKING STRUCTURE

Revolution of Depth

AlexNet, 8 layers
(ILSVRC 2012)

VGG, 19 layers
(ILSVRC 2014)

GoogleNet, 22 layers
(ILSVRC 2014)

Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, & Jian Sun. "Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition". CVPR 2016.

Revolution of Depth

AlexNet, 8 layers
(ILSVRC 2012)

VGG, 19 layers
(ILSVRC 2014)

ResNet, **152 layers**
(ILSVRC 2015)

**I WAS WINNING
IMAGENET**

**UNTIL A
DEEPER MODEL
CAME ALONG**

Image category prediction

Revolution of Depth

Revolution of Depth

PASCAL VOC 2007 Object Detection mAP (%)

*w/ other improvements & more data

Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, & Jian Sun. "Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition". CVPR 2016.

Building blocks

- Network in network
- Inception module
- ResNet: Residual modules

Network in network

(a) Linear convolution layer

(b) Mlpconv layer

M. Lin, Q. Chen, and S. Yan, [Network in network](#), ICLR 2014

GoogLeNet

C. Szegedy et al., [Going deeper with convolutions](#), CVPR 2015

Inception v2, v3

- Regularize training with [batch normalization](#), reducing importance of auxiliary classifiers
- More variants of inception modules with aggressive factorization of filters

Deep Residual Learning

- $F(x)$ is a residual mapping w.r.t. identity

- If identity were optimal, easy to set weights as 0
- If optimal mapping is closer to identity, easier to find small fluctuations

* ResNet-110 on CIFAR-10

$h(x) = x$
error: 6.6%

$h(x) = 0.5x$
error: 12.4%

$h(x) = \text{gate} \cdot x$
error: 8.7%

$h(x) = \text{gate} \cdot x$
error: 12.9%

shortcuts
blocked by
multiplications

$h(x) = \text{conv}(x)$
error: 12.2%

$h(x) = \text{dropout}(x)$
error: > 20%

Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, & Jian Sun. "Identity Mappings in Deep Residual Networks". arXiv 2016.

Very smooth forward propagation

$$x_L = x_l + \sum_{i=l}^{L-1} F(x_i)$$

- Any x_l is **directly** forward-prop to any x_L , plus **residual**.
- Any x_L is an **additive** outcome.
 - in contrast to **multiplicative**: $x_L = \prod_{i=l}^{L-1} W_i x_l$

Very smooth backward propagation

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial x_l} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial x_L} \left(1 + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \sum_{i=1}^{L-1} F(x_i) \right)$$

- Any $\frac{\partial E}{\partial x_l}$ is **directly** back-prop to any $\frac{\partial E}{\partial x_l'}$ plus **residual**.
- Any $\frac{\partial E}{\partial x_l}$ is **additive**; unlikely to vanish
 - in contrast to **multiplicative**: $\frac{\partial E}{\partial x_l} = \prod_{i=l}^{L-1} W_i \frac{\partial E}{\partial x_L}$

Design principles

- Reduce filter sizes (except possibly at the lowest layer), factorize filters aggressively
- Use 1x1 convolutions to reduce and expand the number of feature maps judiciously
- Use skip connections and/or create multiple paths through the network

CNNs: Encoder – Decoder networks

Fully convolutional network (FCN)

- Long et al., *Fully convolutional networks for semantic segmentation*, CVPR 2015
 - Deconvolution to upsample segmentation.
 - Skip connections to combine multi-scale info for better accuracy.
 - Popularized fully conv net (previously [LeCun '98, Farabet '13])

THE ROLE OF DATA

Number of categories vs. number of instances

2009

2012

ImageNet

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=umRdt3zGgpU>

Quadcopter Navigation in the Forest using Deep Neural Networks

QUADCOPTER NAVIGATION IN THE FOREST

TRAIL FOLLOWING UNDER THE TREE CANOPY

0:04 / 4:56

- robot autonomously follows a typical forest trail
- useful to quickly explore an area for wilderness search and rescue missions
- robot perceives the trail only using an ordinary color camera

 trail heading left

 trail straight ahead

 trail heading right

which direction is the trail heading to?

How the classifier works

10
layers

150K
weights

500K
neurons

57M
connections

How we solved the problem

1:06

output

Training the classifier

Training the classifier

Looking to work on tasks? [Sign in as a Worker](#) | [Learn more](#)

amazonmechanicalturk Overview Features Pricing Help Developer Resources Customers [Sign in as a Requester](#)

Amazon Mechanical Turk

Access a global, on-demand, 24x7 workforce

[Get started with Amazon Mechanical Turk](#)

Amazon Mechanical Turk (MTurk) is a crowdsourcing marketplace that makes it easier for individuals and businesses to outsource their processes and jobs to a distributed workforce who can perform these tasks virtually. This could include anything from conducting simple data validation and research to more subjective tasks like survey participation, content moderation, and more. MTurk enables companies to harness the collective intelligence, skills, and insights from a global workforce to streamline business processes, augment data collection and analysis, and accelerate machine learning development.

While technology continues to improve, there are still many things that human beings can do much more effectively than computers, such as moderating content, performing data deduplication, or research. Traditionally, tasks like this have been accomplished by hiring a large temporary workforce, which is time consuming, expensive and difficult to scale, or have gone undone. Crowdsourcing is a good way to break down a manual, time-consuming project into smaller, more manageable tasks to be completed by distributed workers over the Internet (also known as 'microtasks').

Firefox File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Window Help

Web Posta EHU :: Log in x robando a Brice Retailleau x Amazon Mechanical Turk x +

https://www.mturk.com

noticias de gipuzkoa

Optimize efficiency

MTurk is well-suited to take on simple and repetitive tasks in your workflows which need to be handled manually. Using MTurk to outsource microtasks ensures that work gets done quickly, while freeing up time and resources for the company – so internal staff can focus on higher value activities.

Increase flexibility

Scaling up and down a workforce isn't the easiest undertaking. With access to a global, on-demand, 24x7 workforce, MTurk enables businesses and organizations to get work done easily and quickly when they need it – without the difficulty associated with dynamically scaling your in-house workforce.

Reduce cost

MTurk offers a way to effectively manage labor and overhead costs associated with hiring and managing a temporary workforce. By leveraging the skills of distributed Workers on a pay-per-task model, you can significantly lower costs while achieving results that might not have been possible with just a dedicated team.

How it works

MTurk offers developers access to a diverse, on-demand workforce through a flexible user interface or direct integration with a simple API. Organizations can harness the power of crowdsourcing via MTurk for a range of use cases, such as microwork, human insights, and machine learning development.

```
graph LR; Requesters[Requesters have tasks they need to be completed] --> Marketplace[MTurk Marketplace]; Marketplace --> Workers[Workers want to earn money and work on interesting tasks];
```

matsumoto-1401.pdf wiitschko-1501.pdf tesis doctoral...pdf cerezos en flo...mp4 wroclaw-biibo-...pdf

What is going on inside?

What is going on inside?

- Visualization of the representation achieved by the network
 - What is the general image closest to the representation of a given one?
 - What is the general image generated by the maximal activation of unit?
- Acknowledgments: A Vedaldi MISS 2016

Image representations

An **encoder** maps the data into a **vectorial representation**

Facilitate labelling of images, text, sound, videos, ...

Modern convolutional nets

3

Excellent **performance** in image understanding tasks

Learn a sequence of **general-purpose representations**

Millions of parameters learned from data

The “**meaning**” of the representation is **unclear**

Finding a Pre-Image

A simple yet general and effective method

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} \|\Phi(\mathbf{x}) - \Phi_0\|_2^2$$

Image

Representation

Reconstruction

Pre-Image

Start from **random noise**

Optimize using stochastic **gradient descent**

Inversion

AlexNet
[Krizhevsky et al. 2012]

Inverting a Deep CNN

Original Image

CNNs = visual codes?

Activation Maximization

Look for an image that maximally activates a **specific feature component**

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} -\langle \mathbf{e}_k, \Phi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle + R_{TV}(\mathbf{x}) + R_{\alpha}(\mathbf{x})$$

Emphasise patterns that are detected by a certain representation

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} -\langle \Phi(\mathbf{x}_0), \Phi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle + R_{TV}(\mathbf{x}) + R_{\alpha}(\mathbf{x})$$

Key differences:

- ▶ the starting point **is** the image \mathbf{x}_0
- ▶ particular configurations of features are emphasized, not individual features

Caricaturization (VGG-M)

input

conv2

conv3

conv4

Caricaturization (VGG-M)

conv5

fc6

fc7

fc8

Generation by moment matching

53

Moment matching

- ▶ Content statistics: same as inversion
- ▶ Style statistics: cross-channel correlations

$$\mathbf{x}^* = \operatorname{argmin}_{\mathbf{x}} E(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{x}_{\text{content}}, \mathbf{x}_{\text{style}})$$

Vinci

Vincci

ADVERSARIAL ATTACKS

Adversarial attacks

- Examples
- Why?
- Methods

Adversarial Examples

58% panda

+ .007 ×

=

99% gibbon

(Goodfellow et al, 2014)

Correct

Perturbation

Wrong

Correct

Perturbation

Wrong

$$\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{v}) \neq \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}),$$

where \mathbf{K} is a classifier, \mathbf{X} is input image, \mathbf{v} is perturbation.

Intriguing properties of neural networks, Szegedy et al. - 2013

Rubbish

- noisy meaningless pictures that achieve high confidence classification

Why? : Models are too linear

X	2	-1	3	-2	2	2	1	-4	5	1	← input example
W	-1	-1	1	-1	1	-1	1	1	-1	1	← weights
adversarial x	1.5	-1.5	3.5	-2.5	2.5	1.5	1.5	-3.5	4.5	1.5	

class 1 score before:

$$-2 + 1 + 3 + 2 + 2 - 2 + 1 - 4 - 5 + 1 = -3$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{probability of class 1 is } 1/(1+e^{(-(-3))}) = 0.0474$$

$$-1.5+1.5+3.5+2.5+2.5-1.5+1.5-3.5-4.5+1.5 = 2$$

$$P(y = 1 | x; w, b) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(w^T x + b)}} = \sigma(w^T x + b)$$

Evolutionary Approach

Deep Neural Networks are Easily Fooled: High Confidence Predictions for Unrecognizable Images - Nguyen, et al - 2014

Universal Adversarial Perturbations

Sample universal perturbations

(a) CaffeNet

(b) VGG-F

(c) VGG-16

(d) VGG-19

(e) GoogLeNet

(f) ResNet-152

The anatomy of an adversarial attack

Demonstration of how adversarial attacks against various medical AI systems might be executed without requiring any overtly fraudulent misrepresentation of the data.

Original image

+ 0.04 ×

Adversarial noise

Adversarial example

Dermatoscopic image of a benign melanocytic nevus, along with the diagnostic probability computed by a deep neural network.

Perturbation computed by a common adversarial attack technique. See (7) for details.

Combined image of nevus and attack perturbation and the diagnostic probabilities from the same deep neural network.

Diagnosis: Benign

Adversarial rotation (8)

Diagnosis: Malignant

The patient has a history of back pain and chronic alcohol abuse and more recently has been seen in several...

Adversarial text substitution (9)

The patient has a history of lumbago and chronic alcohol dependence and more recently has been seen in several...

Opioid abuse risk: High

Opioid abuse risk: Low

277.7 Metabolic syndrome
429.9 Heart disease, unspecified
278.00 Obesity, unspecified

Adversarial coding (13)

401.0 Benign essential hypertension
272.0 Hypercholesterolemia
272.2 Hyperglyceridemia
429.9 Heart disease, unspecified
278.00 Obesity, unspecified

Reimbursement: Denied

Reimbursement: Approved

Adversarial attacks on medical machine learning

Samuel G. Finlayson, John D. Bowers, Joichi Ito, Jonathan L. Zittrain, Andrew L. Beam and Isaac S. Kohane

Science 363 (6433), 1287-1289.
DOI: 10.1126/science.aaw4399

Generative Adversarial Networks

Goodfellow 2019

A Cambrian Explosion of Machine Learning Research Topics

Generative Modeling: Sample Generation

Training Data
(CelebA)

Sample Generator
(Karras et al, 2017)

Generative Adversarial Networks

4.5 years of progress on faces

2014

2015

2016

2017

2018

(Goodfellow 2019)

2 Years of Progress on ImageNet

Odena et al
2016

Miyato et al
2017

Zhang et al
2018

Brock et al
2018

(Odena 2018)

Adversarial Training

ML model learns
parameters

Attacker chooses input point

(Goodfellow et al 2014, Farley and Goodfellow 2016)

GAN's Architecture

- Z is some random noise (Gaussian/Uniform).
- Z can be thought as the latent representation of the image.

Training Discriminator

Training Generator

Deep Convolutional GANs (DCGANs)

Generator Architecture

Key ideas:

- Replace FC hidden layers with Convolutions
 - **Generator:** Fractional-Strided convolutions
- Use Batch Normalization after each layer
- **Inside Generator**
 - Use ReLU for hidden layers
 - Use Tanh for the output layer

Laplacian Pyramid of Adversarial Networks

Figure 2 in the original paper.

Training Procedure:

Models at each level are trained independently to learn the required representation.

applications

- Grasping learning
- Image to image translation
- Text to image translation
- Simulation of aging

GraspGAN

(Bousmalis et al, 2017)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1OIPjt4LMP4>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TDUKp5ebpqc>

GraspGAN

(Bousmalis et al, 2017)

Sim-to-real via sim-to-sim

(James et al, 2018)

(Goodfellow 2018)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nilcJY5Kdt8>

Image-to-Image Translation

Figure 1 in the original paper.

Isola, P., Zhu, J. Y., Zhou, T., & Efros, A. A. "Image-to-image translation with conditional adversarial networks". arXiv preprint arXiv:1611.07004. (2016).

Text-to-Image Synthesis

Motivation

Given a text description, generate images closely associated.

Uses a conditional GAN with the generator and discriminator being condition on “dense” text embedding.

this small bird has a pink breast and crown, and black primaries and secondaries.

the flower has petals that are bright pinkish purple with white stigma

this magnificent fellow is almost all black with a red crest, and white cheek patch.

this white and yellow flower have thin white petals and a round yellow stamen

Figure 1 in the original paper.

Face Aging with Conditional GANs

- Differentiating Feature: Uses an *Identity Preservation Optimization* using an auxiliary network to get a better approximation of the latent code (z^*) for an input image.
- Latent code is then conditioned on a discrete (one-hot) embedding of age categories.

Figure 1 in the original paper.

Sideline: autoencoders

Variational Autoencoder (VAE)

Variational Autoencoder (2013) work prior to GANs (2014)

- **Explicit Modelling of $P(X|z; \theta)$** , we will drop the θ in the notation.
- $z \sim P(z)$, which we can sample from, such as a Gaussian distribution.

$$P(X) = \int P(X|z; \theta)P(z)dz$$

- Maximum Likelihood --- **Find θ to maximize $P(X)$** , where X is the data.
- Approximate with samples of z

$$P(X) \approx \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n P(X|z_i)$$

Common VAE architecture

Fully Connected (Initially Proposed)

Common Architecture (convolutional) similar to DCGAN.

Disentangle latent factor

Autoencoder can disentangle latent factors [[MNIST DEMO](#)]:

Image Credit: [Auto-encoding Variational Bayes](#)

http://www.dpkgingma.com/sgvb_mnist_demo/demo.html

Deep reinforcement learning

What is deep RL, and why should we care?

sensorimotor loop

Action
(run away)

Example: robotics

robotic control pipeline

tiny, highly specialized “visual cortex” tiny, highly specialized “motor cortex”

sensorimotor loop

Atari games:

Q-learning:

V. Mnih, K. Kavukcuoglu, D. Silver, A. Graves, I. Antonoglou, et al. "Playing Atari with Deep Reinforcement Learning". (2013).

Policy gradients:

J. Schulman, S. Levine, P. Moritz, M. I. Jordan, and P. Abbeel. "Trust Region Policy Optimization". (2015).
 V. Mnih, A. P. Badia, M. Mirza, A. Graves, T. P. Lillicrap, et al. "Asynchronous methods for deep reinforcement learning". (2016).

Real-world robots:

Guided policy search:

S. Levine*, C. Finn*, T. Darrell, P. Abbeel. "End-to-end training of deep visuomotor policies". (2015).

Q-learning:

D. Kalashnikov et al. "QT-Opt: Scalable Deep Reinforcement Learning for Vision-Based Robotic Manipulation". (2018).

Beating Go champions:

Supervised learning + policy

gradients + value functions +

Monte Carlo tree search:

D. Silver, A. Huang, C. J. Maddison, A. Guez, L. Sifre, et al. "Mastering the game of Go with deep neural networks and tree search". Nature (2016).

Reinforcement Learning in a picture

R. S. Sutton and A. G. Barto 2015

- learning what to do to maximize future reward
- general-purpose framework extending sequential decision making when the model of the environment is unknown

RL background

- let's assume MDP $\langle S, A, P, R, s_0 \rangle$
 - RL deals with situation where the environment model P and R is unknown
 - can be generalized to Stochastic Games $\langle S, N, A, P, R \rangle$
- RL agent includes:
 - **policy** $a = \pi(s)$ (deterministic), $\pi(a | s) = \mathbb{P}(a | s)$ (stochastic)
 - **value function** $Q^\pi(a | s) = \mathbb{E}[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t r_t | s, a]$
 - ▶ Bellman Eq.: $Q^\pi(a | s) = \mathbb{E}_{s', a'}[r + \gamma Q^\pi(a' | s') | s, a]$
 - ▶ opt. value functions: $Q^*(s, a) = \mathbb{E}_{s'}[r + \gamma \max_{a'} Q^*(s', a') | s, a]$
 - ▶ opt. policy: $\pi^*(s) = \operatorname{argmax}_a Q^*(s, a)$
 - **model** - learned proxy for environment

RL Types

1. **value-based** RL

- estimate the opt. value function $Q^*(s, a)$
- max. value achievable under *any* policy

2. **policy-based** RL

- search directly for the opt. policy π^*
- i.e. policy yielding max. future reward

3. **model-based** RL

- build a model of the environment
- plan using this model

Q-learning

Algorithm 1 Q-learning

- 1: initialize the Q-function and V values (arbitrarily)
 - 2: **repeat**
 - 3: observe the current state s_t
 - 4: select action a_t and take it
 - 5: observe the reward $R(s_t, a_t, s_{t+1})$
 - 6: $Q_{t+1}(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow (1 - \alpha_t)Q_t(s_t, a_t) + \alpha_t(R(s_t, a_t, s_{t+1}) + \gamma V_t(s_{t+1}))$
 - 7: $V_{t+1}(s) \leftarrow \max_a Q_t(s, a)$
 - 8: **until** convergence
-

Q-learning

- **model-free** method

- *temporal-difference* version:

- $Q(s, a) \leftarrow Q(s, a) + \alpha (r + \underbrace{\gamma \max_{a'} Q(s', a')}_{\text{value based on next state}} - Q(s, a))$

- converges to Q^* , V^* iff $0 \leq \alpha_t < \infty$, $\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \alpha_t = \infty$ and $\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \alpha_t^2 < \infty$

- *zero-sum Stochastic Games*:

- cannot simply use $Q_i^\pi : S \times A_i \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ but rather $Q_i^\pi : S \times A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

- **minimax-Q** converges to NE

- **R-max**: converge to ϵ - Nash with prob. $(1 - \delta)$ in poly. # steps (*PAC learn*)

Q-Networks

- $Q^*(s, a) \approx Q(s, a, \mathbf{w})$
- treat right hand side $r + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(s', a', \mathbf{w})$ of Bellman's Eq. as target
- minimize **MSE loss** $l = (r + \max_{a'} Q(s', a', \mathbf{w}) - Q(s, a, \mathbf{w}))^2$ by **stochastic gradient descent**

DQN in Atari

David Silver, Google DeepMind

DQN in Atari - setting

- state stack of raw pixels from last 4 frames
- actions 18 joystick/button positions
- reward delta in score
- learn $Q(s, a)$

David Silver, Google DeepMind

DQN in Atari - results

DQN improvements

- **Double DQN** removes bias caused by $\max_a Q(\cdot)$
 - current QN - w used to select actions
 - old QN - w^- used to evaluate actions
- **Prioritized Replay** weight experience according to DQN error (stored in PQ)
- **Duelling Network** split Q-Network into:
 - action-independent value function
 - action-dependent advantage function

General Reinforcement Learning Architecture (GORILA)

Deep Policy Network

- parametrize the policy π by a DNN and use SGD to optimize weights \mathbf{u}
 - $\pi(a | s, \mathbf{u})$ or $\pi(s, \mathbf{u})$
 - $\max_{\mathbf{u}} L(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbb{E}[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t r_t | \pi(\cdot, \mathbf{u})]$
- policy gradients:
 - $\frac{\partial L(\mathbf{u})}{\partial \mathbf{u}} = \mathbb{E}[\frac{\partial \log \pi(a|s, \mathbf{u})}{\partial \mathbf{u}} Q^{\pi}(s, a)]$ for *stochastic* policy $\pi(a | s, \mathbf{u})$
 - $\frac{\partial L(\mathbf{u})}{\partial \mathbf{u}} = \mathbb{E}[\frac{\partial Q^{\pi}(s, a)}{\partial a} \frac{\partial a}{\partial \mathbf{u}}]$ for *deterministic* policy $a = \pi(s)$ where a is cont. and Q diff.
- variations: *Actor-Critic alg.*, *A3C*, *Fictitious Self-Play*

Game Theory 101

normal-form game $G = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A}, u)$

- $\mathcal{N} = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ - players
- $\mathcal{A} = \times_{i \in \mathcal{N}} A_i$ - pure strategies (actions)
 - $\Pi = \times_i \Pi_i = \times_i \Delta(A_i)$ - mixed strategies
- $u = (u_1, \dots, u_n)$, $u_i : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ - utilities

best response

$$BR_i(\pi_{-i}) = \{\pi_i \in \Pi_i \mid \forall \pi'_i \neq \pi_i : u_i(\pi_i, \pi_{-i}) \geq u_i(\pi'_i, \pi_{-i})\}$$

Nash equilibrium

$$NE(G) = \{\pi \in \Pi \mid \forall i \in \mathcal{N} : \pi_i \in BR_i(\pi_{-i})\}$$

Fictitious Self Play (FSP)

■ fictitious play (FP)

1. initialize beliefs about the opponent's strategy
2. play a best response to the assessed strategy of the opponent
3. observe the opponent's actual play and update beliefs accordingly, *goto 2*

■ fictitious self play (FSP)

- DQN with experience replay learns “BR” to opponent policies
- policy network learns an average of BRs

$$\frac{\partial l}{\partial \mathbf{w}} = \frac{\partial \log \pi_{\mathbf{w}}(a | s)}{\partial \mathbf{w}}$$

- actions a sample mix of policy network and best response

Go

The Rules of Go

(a) capture

(b) territory

- start empty board
- move place one stone (of your color)
- goal surround
- win control more than half of the board

Go in Theory

- 2-players (just me and the opponent)
- zero-sum game (win for me = loss for opponent)
- perfect information
- finite (the game rules ensure this)
- NE exists and we can search for it:
 - minimax
 - alpha-beta
 - negascout

Go in Reality

there is $O(b^d)$ game states where $b \approx 250$ and $d \approx 150$

$t \leq 2015$

- the strongest Go programs are based on MCTS
- enhanced by policies that are trained to predict human expert moves
 - early rules hand-made
 - later ML based on simple features (lin. comb. of inputs)
- knowledge learned:
 - (i) fast (simple) knowledge used for move selection in simulation (*rollout policy*)
 - (ii) slower (better) knowledge used for move ordering in tree search (*SL policy*)

name
age
rank
titles
power
results
experience

Science

March 9-15, 2016

Lee Sedol

33

9 dan prof.

18

1 brain

loss, loss, loss, **win**, loss

c · 1k games

AlphaGo

2

none

0

1200 CPU and 200 GPU

win, win, win, loss, **win**

c · 1M self-play games

AlphaGo Design

- normal search - MCTS
- simulation (rollout) policy - relatively normal
- supervised learning (SL) policy from master games - in details, more data
- **RL from self-play for value network**
- **RL from self-play for policy network**

Value Network

Convolutional Neural Network

Policy Network

Move probabilities

Reducing d with Value Network

Reducing b with Policy Network

Deep RL in AlphaGo

SL of Policy Networks

network 12 layer convolutional NN

training data 30M position from human experts (KGS 5+ dan)

training alg. max. likelihood by SGD

$$\Delta\sigma \propto \frac{\partial \log p_\sigma(a | s)}{\partial \sigma}$$

training time 4 weeks on 50 GPUs (Google Cloud)

results 57% accuracy on held out test data

- state-of-the art was 44%

RL of Value Networks

network 12 layer convolutional NN

training data 30M games of self-play

idea

$$v^p(s) = \mathbb{E}[z_t | s_t = s, a_{t,\dots,T} \sim p]$$

$$v_\theta(s) \approx v^{p_\rho}(s) \approx v^*(s)$$

training alg. min. MSE by SGD

$$\Delta\theta \propto \frac{\partial v_\theta(s)}{\partial \theta} (z - v_\theta(s))$$

training time 1 week on 50 GPUs (Google Cloud)

results **first strong position eval. function**

RL of Policy Networks

network 12 layer convolutional NN

training data games of self-play between policy networks

training alg. max. wins z by policy gradient RL

$$\Delta\rho \propto \frac{\partial \log p_\rho(a | s)}{\partial \rho} z$$

training time 1 week on 50 GPUs (Google Cloud)

results 80% vs. SL network p_σ

- raw network \sim 3 amateur dan

MCTS in AlphaGo

- each edge stores:

action value $Q(s, a)$

visit count $N(s, a)$

prior prob. $P(s, a)$ (initialized to $P(s, a) = p_\sigma(a | s)$)

- at each step t we select in state s_t :

$$a_t = \operatorname{argmax}_a (Q(s_t, a) + u(s_t, a))$$

- $u(s, a) \propto \frac{P(s, a)}{1 + N(s, a)}$ decays with repeated visits (encourages exploration)

- leaf node s_L is evaluated in two different ways:

$$V(s_L) = (1 - \lambda)v_\theta(s_L) + \lambda z_L$$

1. by value network $v_\theta(s_L)$

2. by outcome $z_L \sim^* p_\tau$

AlphaGo: results

Dexterous manipulation

- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jJtBII8I_OM
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jwSbzNHGfIM>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mpGK4zbdi6g>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I9U8X6I1vow>